

Consumers' Behavior toward Plant-Based Milk Alternatives [†]

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Abstract: In recent years, more people have expressed interest in Plant-Based Milk Alternatives (PBMA). Our research focused on Greek consumers to examine consumer behavior regarding PBMA. Using relevant literature, a questionnaire was designed and distributed both online and through personal interviews. The sample was random and concerned 576 consumers from the Greek mainland, of which 53.5% were women and 46.5% were men, aged 18 to 80. The Health Belief (HBM) and Stimulus Organism Response (SOR) models were used to design the questionnaire, while Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied for the interpretation of the survey results. PCA showed that consumers' perception of PBMA, and their willingness to consume them or influence others to do so, are the most significant variables. Furthermore, Linear Regression Analysis revealed that PBMA are primarily purchased by younger and more highly educated consumers. The results of the research can contribute to the improvement of PBMA retail marketing strategies in Greece.

Keywords: PBMA; consumer behavior; principal component analysis (PCA)

1. Introduction

In recent years, the consumption of plant-based beverages has shown an upward trend. According to Nielsen IQ [1], for the year 2021–2022, milk and dairy alternatives' total dollar growth increased by 6.8% compared to the previous year and 34.6% over the previous 3 years. The same research states that even though alternative milk consumption has increased significantly, the plant-based industry accounts for only 15% of total milk sales. Markets & Markets [2] projects that the global market for dairy alternatives will grow by USD 17.5 billion until 2027, reaching USD 44.8 billion. Despite the growth tendency, many consumers still find it difficult to switch from traditional milk to milk alternatives. More specifically, a recent European study, including German, French and Polish consumers, indicated that people are not ready to give up on dairy products entirely, whilst the reason for adding dairy substitutes to their diets is primarily out of curiosity, the need to explore new things and to expand their diet [3]. According to Schiano et al. [4], many parents still link dairy milk with positive characteristics, making them more persuasive than plant-based alternatives. On the other hand, Moss et al.'s [5] survey states that consumers have correlated milk alternatives with health benefits, sustainability and sensory attributes. Research from Denmark by Martinez-Padilla et al. [6] indicates that taste, followed by health and naturalness, are the main motivators for the consumption of PBMA, while negative indicators include the belief that PBMA are artificial and heavily processed.

Research opinions on the consumption of plant-based beverages are divided. Considering that plant-based milk alternatives are an ongoing trend, this study aimed to examine Greek consumers' attitudes regarding those products. The goal is, therefore, to be able to define the main factors leading consumers to either choose these beverages or not, in comparison to conventional milk, and their awareness of those products, their concerns and their future intentions to consume them, using a sufficient and representative sample

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of respondents. Furthermore, PCA was performed. The results showed that consumers' perceptions of PBMA and their willingness to consume and promote them are the most important variables. Additionally, the Linear Regression Analysis indicated that PBMA are predominantly bought by younger consumers with a higher education level.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1. Questionnaire Construction

Initially, a review of the literature on consumer behavior theories was conducted to identify the most essential aspects influencing consumer perceptions and preferences. The HBM was used to examine the relationship between health-related factors and consumer behavior. In addition, the SOR model was used to clarify how direct and indirect social environment stimuli contribute to making these decisions, and how the consumer evaluates the product through consumption experience. The questionnaire is divided into two main categories. The first category included demographic questions, while the second one concerned consumers' knowledge of plant-based milk alternatives, awareness of their consumption, consumer behavior, health-related questions, and willingness to consume. The questionnaire was distributed to consumers from the Greek mainland, aged 18 to 80, over the course of five months, starting from November 2022, through both online and in-person interviews. In-person interviews were used to encourage more people, especially older people and those with little or no technological background, to participate in the survey.

2.2. Statistical Analysis

PCA and Linear Regression Analysis was used to analyze the results. PCA allows a considerable amount of information to be condensed into a small number of variables, which indicate very distinct and clear characteristics of the phenomenon under assessment. The order in which the components appear reflects their relative weight, resulting in a systematic ranking of the factors. Thus, the first component, in order of appearance, holds more importance than the second, and the second more than the third, and so on. Variables were expressed on a Likert scale from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating total disagreement and 5 total agreement with each statement. KMO was calculated to ensure that PCA results were credible. Linear Regression Analysis was used to correlate the factors emerging from PCA with the socioeconomic characteristics of the sample.

3. Results

3.1. Demographic Information

Demographic data showed that 53.5% of the sample corresponded to female participants, while male participants accounted for the remaining 46.5%. Furthermore, the data indicated that 21.53% of the participants fell within the 18–24 age group, 20.49% in the 25–34 age group, 22.40% in the 35–44 age group, 20.66% in the 45–59 age group and 14.93% aged 60 and above.

3.2. Consumer Behavior Analysis

For the consumer behavior analysis, PCA was used to examine how the variables are interconnected, and if there are any relations among them. PCA was performed with variables from the second part of the questionnaire. The KMO indicator was 0.847, close to 1 and of high significance, meaning that the sample was adequate for PCA analysis and that the study was valid.

PCA produced seven components, of which the two most significant will be further discussed. Factor 1 indicates that consumers' perceptions of plant-based beverages and traditional milk are related to their interest in drinking plant-based milk alternatives and their willingness to influence others (Figure 1). All the variables in the second component are grouped under the same heading: health-related questions. Consumers are concerned

about a variety of health issues that can be induced by the consumption of dairy milk, including diabetes, cardiovascular disease, osteoporosis, and chronic fatigue.

Figure 1. Questions related to the first component (factor loadings), authors' elaboration.

Linear Regression Analysis indicated that participants' age and educational status affect both the first and second component. The results for the first factor showed that most younger consumers believe that PBMA are healthier than regular milk, whereas older consumers strongly disagree with this statement. In addition, even though younger people are more interested in buying PBMA for their kids in the future, older people do not share the same interest. Another significant result shows that only highly educated consumers are willing to buy PBMA for their children. The results of the second component reveal that older customers were more anxious about facing cardiovascular disease or osteoporosis than younger people. Furthermore, educated consumers are less concerned regarding these health issues, as was expected.

4. Discussion

It is important to mention that in this study consumers with higher educational status were more interested in purchasing PBMA. This is verifying Kriwy and Mecking's survey [7], which connects a high level of education with organic food consumption. Differences in food perceptions are known to be influenced by traditions and cultures, as is the case for consumer surveys in Poland, Germany and France [3]. In most relevant research papers only a small group of young consumers participated, clarifying the parent perspective on PBMA consumption. For this reason, the findings of this study are significant to fulfill this need.

5. Conclusions

According to the research findings, there is a growing interest in plant-based milk alternatives among Greek consumers. This tendency, however, is more popular among younger and more educated consumers. Overall, the study can help inform retailers and marketers in Greece about this upward trend and the alternative ways to effectively promote and commercialize plant-based milk alternatives.

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